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An Assessment of Factors Responsible for Voter Apathy in Nigeria: Empirical Evidences from 2023 Presidential Election in Jigawa State

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ABSTRACT

In every democracy, election is the essential ingredient that allows transition from one regime to the other. It is the means and process by which the electorates decide who and which group administers the affairs of the country based upon their perceived conviction on the agenda and programmer presented by the group, Unfortunately, what is obtained in Africa and Nigeria in particular is different as voter apathy continues to be a major concern after every poll. This paper examined the voter Apathy in general election and assessing the factors responsible for voter apathy in the elections. Rational choice theory was adopted as the mental map for the work. To achieve the aim of this study, the study adopted cross sectional survey research design and relied on both primary and secondary source of data through the help of structured questionnaire. The result obtained from administered questionnaire was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation. The results revealed among other things that one of the major factors responsible for low voter turnout in Nigeria is lack of fulfillment of campaign promises by the political office holders. The study recommended among other things compulsory voting with strict penalty. the uses of advance technology to ease the process and that there should be proper sensitization of electorates by all necessary stakeholders and other relevant authorities by encouraging electorates to use their power judiciously by voting out candidates who fail to fulfill campaign promises as this will serve as deterrent for other political aspirants.

Keywords: Voter apathy, election, electorates, and democracy,

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is an inter-cultural state which is known for her ethnic and cultural diversity. The need to involve citizens in the affairs of governance is one of the reasons that validate the modern democratic thinking. Unfortunately, Nigeria has recorded military intervention since the country gained independence in 1960 not until 1999 till date that the country has been experiencing stable democracy without military

intervention. After the country returned to civil rule in 1999 during the fourth republic, the country has recorded uninterrupted democratic governance for over two decades. (Reynolds, 2012)

Though, not without some hindrances and one of these challenges is voter apathy which has been on an increase in every election. In 2003, the number of voter turnout was 69.1% of registered voters and unfortunately, the last election that was held in 2019 saw a total decline in voter turnout to 34.75% as reported by the election umpire. The decline in voter turnout has been consistent since 2003 and this continuous drop in the voter turnout informed this research study to examine the factors responsible for low voter turnout in Nigeria for the Presidential Election of 2023. (I-IDEA 2019)

Basically, the recurring decimal of voter apathy in Nigeria is not exclusive to national elections but has over the years reflected in sub-national elections such as gubernatorial and local polls. The widespread of voter apathy or low voter turnout observed in the recent 2023 general elections has elicited serious concerns, as earlier noted, among Nigerians and international election observers on what it portends to the country's fledgling democracy and way forward (Okeke and Idike 2013),

However, the 2023 Presidential Election is one of the most keenly and closely contested in the history of Nigerian Presidential Elections since the colonial and post-independence period. The election was heralded with tensions, accusations and counter-accusations, intense campaign, trade of blames by the ruling and major opposition parties and other related issues. (Fagunwa 2015). The 2023 presidential Election witnessed a retrogressive outcome in comparison with the 2019 General Election. The 2019 General Election was unanimously reported by domestic observers, international monitoring team, civil societies, ruling and opposition parties and voters as fair and credible (Nwangwu, 2019)

furthermore, in 2023 presidential election in Jigawa state recorded a drop in voter turn-out when compare with the 2019 presidential election turn-out. Unfortunately, the percentage of registered voters increases while voters turn out decreases in Jigawa state, for the 2023 presidential election was 34.75% of registered voters while the 2019 Presidential election as reported by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC, 2019). The implication is that 65.25% of the registered voters did not vote. Though, the focus of this study is not to provide answers to the question of whether or not the outcome of the election would have changed if this 65.25% electorates had added their voice through the ballot rather to find out major factors that lead to the refusal of the 65.25% electorates to exercise their civic rights as given to them by virtue of practicing democracy. It is against this backdrop that this study is carried out an assessment of the major factors that result to high voter apathy in the 2023 presidential election in Jigawa state.

Though, the factors that account for low voter turnout differ from continent to continent and from countries to countries. For example, authors such as David Hill claimed that voting legislation and logistical issues lowered voter turnout in the United States; American voting system has traits that are uncommon in other democracies, such as non-automatic voter registration and voting on a weekday (Beregovskiy, 2019). These factors and many more are held responsible for low voter turnout in America.

This study is significant because while some researchers examined other variables (religion, god fatherism, political violence, ethnicity etc.) that may be responsible for the voter apathy in other states of the federation, not much work, if any, has been done on factors responsible for voter apathy in 2023 general elections in Jigawa states. For instance, Faeren (2015) studied Voter Apathy and voter turnout in the 2015 Presidential elections: The Benue state experience and Anthony and Callistus (2017) focused on the ethnicity, religion and voter's behavior: the experience of 2019 presidential election in Nigeria. Omotola and Adekunle (2021) work centred on adoption and use of electronic voting system as an option towards credible elections in Nigeria: Jigawa state as case study. Thus, this paper contributes to extant knowledge on the relationship between election, and voter participation in Nigeria.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW OF RELATED WORKS

Aloysius et al. (2019) investigated voting apathy among the Nigerian electorates in 2023 general elections. The study relied on secondary sources of data. The findings from the study revealed that poor political and voter's education, education, illiteracy, neglect to pick up their permanent voter's cards, the

nature of Nigerian politics is another factor since Nigeria politics, failure of the elected representatives to deliver on promises are the factors that make electorates to find it difficult to participate in the electoral process. The study therefore recommended the provision of security to ensure safety of electorates during and after election.

Babeiya (2013) in his study assessed voter registers and the question of inclusion and exclusion in Tanzania's multiparty elections. The study aimed at investigating whether or not the introduction of permanent voter registers in Tanzania has resolved registration controversies. The research relied on secondary source of data. The study concluded that despite some improvements such as the establishment of a permanent voters' database, voter registration in the country is still marred by numerous anomalies such as a denial of some eligible voters of their registration rights. Likewise, others who register find themselves being disqualified from voting on different grounds, as election observers' reports have revealed.

Snyder (2011) examined factors that impact levels of voting activity among in American. The study used data from the American National Election Survey (ANES) from the years 1972 – 2004. The study revealed that education and political knowledge remain the most important predictors of voter turnout. In addition, the study further revealed that education on voter turnout remains elusive but it is certain that education is still among the most important factors to consider in studying voter turnout and further stated that its vary across space and time.

Seanego and Mogoboya (2019) examined the factors contributing to the decline of votes in South Africa using Mankweng community as a case study. The study adopted survey research design which adopted random sampling of fifteen (15) eligible voters from a total population of twenty-eight (28) from Mankweng community. Open-ended interview was used as instrument of data collection. The study revealed that the youth and elderly believed that the government does not adequately add value to their lives and as such do not see the need to vote.

Mataka and Nkandu (2020) examined the effect of voter apathy on the growth of electoral democracy in Zambia with a focus on Kabwe central constituency. The study relied on a mixed approach as it combined both qualitative and quantitative research. The study reveals that there is a positive co-relationship between voting and the growth of electoral democracy since voting promotes citizen participation which is one of the cardinal elements for the growth of electoral democracy. The study also revealed that factors account for voter apathy include failure to change leadership, failure to honor campaign promises, electoral violence, and religious beliefs, age eligibility, limited voting hours and lack or inadequate voter education.

Nwankwo (2019) examined determinants of voter turnout in Nsukka council of Enugu State, South Eastern Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design for the study. The study adopted stepwise logistic regression in order to remove variables that are not important, leaving the variables that best explain the distribution. The study revealed that age, education, marital status, political trust and partisanship are core predictors of voter turnout in the study area. All these five factors are statistically significant, but among the five elements, only partisanship has a negative effect on voting.

Amanyie, Bariledum and Lucky (2015) examined the effect of electoral violence on political participation in Nigeria with specific reference to Osun State gubernatorial election. The study adopted qualitative approach as data was gathered from secondary sources and analyzed using content analysis. The study hypothesized that there is a correlation between electoral violence and voter apathy. The study revealed that voters' apathy declines with reduced electoral violence and rises with increased transparency, credibility and security.

Michael (2018) examined politics and governance a critique of the 2019 Nigeria presidential election. The study adopted survey research design. Questionnaire was used as instrument of data collection for the study. The result of the analysis shows that political apathy has significant effect on governance in Nigeria and further indicated that good governance has significant effect on the economic growth of Nigeria. Political apathy is a product of electoral violence and it negatively affects upon the electoral process and its outcome.

Falade (2014) examined the extent to which the citizens are involved in political activities. The study adopted mixed method of data collection by using questionnaire as the quantitative instrument and interview schedule was used to obtain qualitative data. The findings of the study revealed that 57% of the participants were not actively involved in political activities. In addition, it was discovered in the study that majority (53%) of the respondents had no confidence in their political leaders.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This paper was anchored on the theoretical construct that “individual always make prudent and logical decisions that offers him greatest satisfaction – given the choices available – and are in his highest self-interest” (Downs, 1957). The rational choice theory according to Haywood (2002:430) based on the assumption that individuals are rationally self-interested actors and make their choices in accordance with the fact of reality. Downs (1957) opined that although rational choice theory emanated from economics however, it is having significant impact on the study of voter behavior and motivation. According to the rational choice theory, if potential voters think their vote is highly likely to make a difference, electoral turnout would be high, and if they believed that their votes are unlikely to make a difference, there would be voter apathy.

In other words, advocates of this theory believe that before an electorate chooses any of the aforementioned options, he would have his reason or reasons. Thus, like most democracies in the world, Nigeria since 1999 has been experiencing voter apathy which seems to be a signal of voter dissatisfaction with the elections and its conducts in the country. Although, voter register book continuously increasing in every election year of 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015 and 2019 but the question begging for answer is why voter turnout continuously declining? The rational choice theory is best explained this political problem in the African largest democracy. By and large Jigawa state, the theory has been criticized on the ground that not all voters vote rationally especially in democracies where vote buying is highly practiced.

FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR VOTER APATHY IN NIGERIA

1. Relationship between the state and the society.

In the social contract that was entered between the people and the state, it was not only the state that was to carry out certain functions or fulfills certain obligations but also the people were expected to do certain things. The people however will not do certain things when the state fails to keep to its own end of the bargain. The apathy in the Nigerian democratic system is only a revelation of the injury, hurt, disappointment and displeasure of Nigerians with the entire democratic system and governance. Voter apathy is a manifestation that can only be corrected by the political class who central to the political problems faced in the country.

The belief that vote does not count in Nigeria, many people dislike voting in elections in Nigeria because of the negative belief that votes do not count in the country. This is built out of years of ballot snatching, mutilation, multiple voting and other vices that have marred the electoral process. The large-scale manipulation and scuttling of the voting process that ends in the announcement of results that do not reflect the needs of the people makes citizens prefer to sit in the comfort of their homes that stand under the scorching heat of the sun to cast a vote that would not count Mill, (2011).

2. Lack of trust in Corrupt Politicians

Many people have lost trust and faith in government and the so-called elected politicians. Many believe that Nigerian politicians will say anything to be elected but once in office, they quickly turn their back on those who put them there. The political class especially in Nigeria has made politics a dirty game, a game of lies and deceit all targeted at arriving at the venue of the national cake. In most cases, people do not see their electorates until the next election and some are rarely seen during campaign because they have the power to hijack the entire electoral process. Most times, Nigerians have to choose between the devil and the deep blue sea because they are skeptical about what each candidate claim to offer Nwolise, (2017).

3. Absence of Effective Security at Voting Centers

Due to the volatile nature of Nigerian election, security presence at election system has a way of boosting the courage of the voters. It is however not surprising that security forces posted to an area ends up absconding due to the volatility of such areas. The presence of security means that the individual is sure that his life will be protected when casting his votes. Taking cognizance of the fact that election ground is more like a battle city where anything can happen.

4. Voter Intimidation

The use of thugs, cultists, criminals and militants to intimidate political opponents and voters has been a trend in Nigerian politics. In some cases, the thugs end up snatching the ballot boxes and mutilating votes. Sadly, the Nigerian security forces in some instance tallies with the government in intimidating voters to vote in a certain candidate. Hence, even with the presence of security forces, Nigerians still maintain an attitude of apprehension over the voting process.

5. Hypercritical Negative Media

Negative political news coverage and political criticisms, which in most cases are not always constructive, create cynicism in many Nigerians. Thus, voters are at times over-fed with falsehood and frightening image of the political environment. In the 2015 general election, the sitting president and his political party, the People Democratic Party (PDP) sponsored wide critical, abusive and inciting statement against the candidate of the opposition party, Muhammadu Buhari. The hate speeches and documentaries went on print, internet and mass media, contributing to heating the media and promoting the divide between the north and the south. Such anomalies are instigation for voter apathy (Okolie, 2009).

6. Literacy and Poverty

Illiteracy and poverty are two powerful forces, which militate against political participation in Nigeria. Victims of these forces have little or no interest in political activities. The lack of awareness on the fundamental human right of the citizens' is responsible for this trend. Because are illiterate, they feel alienated from the system and because people are poor, they feel the system has failed them. The same politicians end up manipulating this same group of persons to sell their votes and bribe them with cups of gari and palm oil to cast their vote.

7. Failed Electoral Promises

The failure of elected political office holders to honor electioneering promises and the imposition of candidates on voters by political parties in no small measure fueled political apathy in the country. The electoral management body cannot also be justified. They have been involved in aiding and abating the selfish aims of these selfish politicians, thereby promoting the collapse of democratic ideals in the country. It should however be noted that Electoral participation is one of the three main indicators of democratic performance Sesan, (2012)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of this study, descriptive research design was adopted. This research design was chosen in order to have a clear picture of the phenomena under our study. The data for this study include secondary and primary data. The secondary data comprise journals, newspapers, library materials, INEC reports and the internet. The primary sources are the direct participant observation by the researcher being an active part of the 2023 presidential election process as supervisor in Roni local government.

By and large, since the researcher wanted to get the voters' opinion (primary data), quantitative method through questionnaires was appropriate. The quantitative method therefore helped the researcher to obtain responses from a large sample from the population of this study. The population for the study consisted of the entire group of eligible Jigawa voters (above 18) across the state – 2,943,107.

However, using Taro Yamane sample size formula, our sample size was 399.95 (400 in approximation). Multi-stage sampling technique was used in order to reach our sample size. Jigawa state was stratified into three senatorial districts and using purposive sampling technique, we picked the local government with the highest registered voters in each of the three senatorial districts of the state as the sample environments.

They are Yankwashi LGA from Jigawa North, Hadejia LGA, Jigawa South and Jigawa West for Dutse LGA. Closed questionnaires which contained two sections (section A focuses on bio-data of the respondents while section B covers questions on the 2023 elections in Jigawa state and the factors responsible of voter apathy) were randomly administered to respondents the 400 respondents in the three local government area. Charts and tables were used in presenting respondents' views on the work under study and simple percentage was used in analyzing them.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

Twenty (20) respondents were used for pilot study to enable researcher to determine whether there is any ambiguity in any of the items and ensured that the instruments elicited the type of data anticipated to answer research questions. The instrument was further reviewed by experts with specialized knowledge in the area of study and those that failed to measure the variables intended were either modified or discarded.

The questionnaire from the pilot study was subjected to reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 70.2% was obtained as shown in Table 1. Hence, the responses generated for all of the variables used in this research were reliable enough for the data analysis. Though, this does not form the main analysis of the study.

Table 1 Reliability Statistics Cronbach's Alpha N of Items.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.702	10

.702 10

3.6 Data Analysis Techniques

Data was edited to identify incomplete questions and internal consistency of the recorded data. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics to enable the researcher to be able to determine the factors that contribute significantly to voter turnout in the 2023 presidential election in Jigawa state. The data was analyzed using Mean and Standard deviation statistical tools using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software version 20.0.

Note: Strongly agree (5)

Agree (4)

Undecided (3)

Disagree (2)

Strongly disagree (1)

Cut off point = $\frac{1+2+3+4+5}{5}$ Cut off point = 3 + 0.5 (margin error)

Cut off point = 3.50 Decision Rule: Any variable that has a mean score of less than 3.5 is not considered as a significant factor and any variable that has a mean score of 3.5 and above is considered as a significant factor that influence voter turnout

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 2 Did you register to vote in the 2023 general election

Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes 410	99.8	99.8	99.8
No 1	2	2	100.
Total 411	100	100	

Source: Researchers' survey (2025)

The Table 2 shows clearly that 410 respondents representing 99.8% registered to participate in the 2023 presidential elections in Jigawa state as eligible voters who are 18years above while only one respondent fails to register as eligible voter. This is an indication that since almost all the respondents registered as

eligible voters, they are the right people to fill the questionnaire since the study focused on registered voters.

Table 3 Did you vote in the 2023 Presidential election in Jigawa state

Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
127	30.9	30.9	30.9	yes
284	69.1	69.1	59.1	no
411	100.0	100.0	100.0	Total

Source: Researchers' survey (2025)

The Table 3 shows clearly that 127 respondents representing 30.9% actually voted in the 2023 presidential elections as eligible voters who are 18years above while 284 respondents fail to cast their vote. This is indications that since most of the respondents fail to vote in the 2023 presidential election, they will be able to tell the factors that made them not to vote in the election and their opinion will be valid.

Table 4 Factors Responsible for voter apathy in the 2023 Presidential election in Jigawa state

s/n	Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	Decision
1	Politicians do not fulfill campaign promises	411	4.40	1.008	Accepted
2	Long queue before voting	411	3.89	1.343	Accepted
3	I do not trust election umpire because my vote will not be counted	411	3.79	1.334	Accepted
4	Malfunction of the card reader machine	411	3.67	1.364	Accepted
5	Violence during election	411	3.60	1.394	Accepted
6	My polling unit is too far from my residence	411	2.64	1.226	Accepted
7	Lack of voter education	411	2.60	1.148	Rejected
8	Limited voting hour	411	2.50	1.107	Rejected
9	Failure to collect my Permanent Voters Card (PVCs)	411	2.37	1.041	Rejected
10	Name not found in the voters' register	411	1.84	384	Rejected

Source: Researchers' survey (2025)

Table 4 shows that the responses of the respondents to items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 with mean scores of 4.40, 3.89, 3.79, 3.67 and 3.60 and standard deviation scores of 1.008, 1.343, 1.334, 1.364 and 1.394 respectively were accepted base on 3.50 cut off point as the factors that led to low voter turnout in the 2023 presidential election held across all the states of the federation in Nigeria. However, items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 revealed means score of 2.64, 2.60, 2.50, 2.37 and 1.84 and standard deviation scores of 1.226, 1.148, 1.107, 1.041 and 0.384 respectively were rejected base on the 3.50 cut off point as factors that made the voters not to turn out to vote in the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria. The findings of this study indicate that some of the voters refused to vote in the 2023 presidential election because the previous government have failed in keeping up with their campaign promises.

This finding conform with previous studies' findings such as Aloysius et al (2019); Nwankwo (2019); Seanego and Mogoboya (2019); Mataka and Nkandu (2020); Yakubu (2012); Idike (2014); Falade (2014) who also found out that failure to fulfill campaign promises is a major factor that influence turnout.

In addition, the study also revealed that the need to stay on the queue for a long time period of time before getting accredited and also to vote which is usually considered to be very hectic especially during

the election because of large number that the election umpire will have to deal with in the course of getting them accredited and voting as well. The finding is in line with similar studies by Stephen (2012).

It was also revealed from the analysis that voters felt there is practically no point in coming out to vote because more often than not, the winner of an election is usually decided even before the commencement of the polls and as such they have lost confidence and trust in the election umpire and this has made many of the voters to refuse to come out to exercise their franchise in the 2023 general election.

This finding is in line with Haime (2017); Babeiya (2013). Also, some of the voters who fail to vote in the 2023 presidential election held that they do not like the method of voting. Though, the method of voting in the election was ballot paper as the INEC has not finalized on the introduction of Electronic Voting (EV) in Nigeria. Lastly, many of the respondents revealed that their refusal to come out to vote is not unconnected to the safety of their lives as election in Nigeria are usually marred by violence which is usually orchestrated by political thugs who are hired by politicians to bring them to power through violent means. This finding is in line with that of Mataka and Nkandu (2020); Amanye et al (2015); Stephen (2012); Michael (2018).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that the major factors responsible for low voter turnout in the 2023 presidential election in Jigawa state include failure of political office holders to fulfill campaign promises they made prior to election, long queue before voting, lack of confidence in election body to conduct free, fair and credible election and violence during election are the major factors responsible for low voter turnout in the 2019 presidential election in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended the following:

- i. Community leaders, religious leaders, youth leaders and other relevant authorities should enlighten the voters on the danger of voter turnout by admonishing voters to vote out non performing political office holders rather than refusing to vote.
- ii The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) should ensure that they deploy enough ad hoc staff to polling unit to save time during election. This will ensure that people do not stay for too long before they can cast their votes during election.
- iii. INEC officials should ensure that they remain independent and autonomous from political influence by not associating with any politician during and after election and where an official is found wanting, he/she be made to face the law
- iv Lastly, government should provide armed security personnel to man polling units across the federation in order to ensure that political thugs do not disturb polls that could scare voters not to be able to come out en masse to exercise their franchise during elections

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